

THE POSSIBILITY OF PRACTICAL APPLICATION OF THE METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING ACMEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE EDUCATORS

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Annotation: In this article, by forming acmeological positions of future teachers in higher educational institutions, they will increase their activity in the educational process, instill a sense of responsibility towards their chosen profession, and provide feedback on the development of various reforms in society. stated.

Key words: socio-economic, independent education, social necessity, acmeological position, innovative and digital, Education and training, scientific-methodical.

Introduction:

Determining the prospects for the development of the new Uzbekistan, and implementing large-scale reforms in order to take a worthy place among the countries of the developed world community. Studying the experiences of the developed countries of the world, taking into account local conditions, economic and intellectual resources, the implementation of fundamental reforms in all spheres of society ensures new achievements. Taking into account the modern requirements, one of the urgent tasks of today is to organize the work of regularly improving the development of cognitive competence in future teachers.

In the scientific research carried out in the world and national education system on the improvement of the qualifications of educational staff, special attention is paid to the high professional potential of future pedagogic personnel, in which the main emphasis is on improving the acmeological competence of specialists in their profession, social scientific research aimed at forecasting the scope of general cultural competencies of managers and pedagogues is being carried out on the basis of expanding their activity through intellectual information systems (e-learning concept), CIVIC international evaluation program (citizenship, political literacy, patriotism, management level development). In this innovative direction, increasing the scope of competences of future pedagogues, improving the mechanisms for developing universal competences of personnel, and training high-potential, flexible and competitive specialists, is one of the urgent issues for the educational system based on the equilibration of integration processes. Such a social phenomenon has become particularly relevant, and in the course of training, in the course of these studies, it is necessary to study the theoretical-methodological foundations of didactic, prognostic, personal, special, acmeological, general cultural and professional competencies of pedagogues, to improve them based on modern requirements, and to improve the quality and efficiency of education. It is important to develop proposals that scientifically justify the quality of education, to improve the quality assessment system of professional development education. In this regard, the topic of the dissertation dedicated to the study of these issues is relevant.

Literature analysis and methodology.

One of the modern trends is to ensure the quality and competitiveness of educational institutions by developing the competence of specialists in the world. In the context of the "Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)" and "European Higher Education Area" (EHEA) concepts adopted at the 70th anniversary session of the UN General Assembly, the model of "competency-based learning" was introduced in personnel training and professional development. Improvement of the mechanisms of continuous development of professional skills based on the humanization of education" was defined as one of the strategic directions. This ensures the integration of advanced foreign experiences of developing general cultural competencies of future pedagogues into the management and educational process along with professional competencies. Modern pedagogical approaches: mutual integration of person-oriented, competence-based, acmeological education, finding their intersection points and using them in a mixed manner in the educational process serve to increase the quality of education, in particular, the effectiveness of literary education. The correctness of this scientific hypothesis can be justified by the following factors:

1. The use of cognitive, personal, cultural and competence paradigms, which are considered leaders in the field of pedagogy, in educational practice requires the use of modern pedagogical approaches in a separate subject or lesson in a mutually integrated manner.

2. It is necessary to take into account all of these paradigms when defining the perspective of educational development and making strategic decisions in the conditions of informatization of education, because they are a specific system and appear as parts of the whole.

3. Placing the learner at the center of the educational process, providing all the necessary conditions for his education (person-oriented approach), identifying and developing their talents (acmeological approach), education none of these approaches deny, but on the contrary, support issues such as the formation of competences (competence approach).

4. Modern pedagogical approaches do not negate each other, on the contrary, they complement each other.

5. Interactive methods have a common feature for modern pedagogical approaches and serve to ensure their interconnection, coherence and relevance.

The acmeological activity of the future teacher consists of the following logically determined actions:

- problematic analysis of the initial state of pedagogical professionalism, self-diagnosis of the person and activity at the current level of professionalism;
- development of a personal acmeological project (conceptualization, technology and provision of resources);
- constant redesign (correction) of personal and professional development based on considerations arising from the existing and/or emerging situation in the professional field;
- reflection on the advantages and disadvantages of professional and pedagogical activities.

Acmeological activity is a student's conscious and steady aspiration as a subject of professional development to a high level of professionalism, to fully reveal his resources, to reach the maximum possible level at this stage of social and individual development. Acmeological activity implies a conscious and steady effort of the student to reach a high level

of professionalism as a subject of professional development. Implementation of acmeological activity in educational practice is carried out through the system of acmeological skills. The following should be distinguished as the main groups of acmeological skills: 5

- ❖ the ability to analyze and verify the state of quasi-professional activity;
- ❖ the ability to predict and design an acmeogram;
- ❖ the ability to implement and reflect an acmeogram.

The main task of acmeological activity is the development of acmeograms, which should be carried out on the basis of a project-based approach (project-based). A teacher's acmeogram is a document that shows the individual "trajectory" of his rise to the heights of professionalism, the program for moving from one level of professionalism to another, to a higher level. A teacher's acmeogram is a tool for promoting a teacher to professionalism, a teacher's achievement of his professional "acme", as well as a means of self-control over this action.

The teacher's acmeogram should be related to the teacher's professionogram. The professional profile reflects the social requirements for the professional activity and personality of the specialist. The professionogram reflects the list of socially approved professional tasks, professional techniques and technologies, as well as the list of personal qualities of a specialist that are acceptable for this profession.

Several variants of the teacher's professionogram are described in the literature. The professional profile of the teacher reveals the features of successful implementation of professional activity, the requirements for achieving a socially acceptable result. Acmeogram reveals ways to raise the teacher's professional skills to higher levels. Therefore, the acmeogram can include the tasks of improving the teacher's qualifications. For example, mastering new teaching methods, developing one's individual style, etc.

Results.

The creative side of the acmeological activity expressed in the development of the creativity and creative potential of the future teacher, as well as the manifestation and implementation of the future teacher's personality in the process of learning, is of particular importance. The design of his personal and professional development, the search for the most effective coordination that leads to the optimal achievement of professional "acmeology", as well as the formation of the individual activity style of the future teacher are personal characteristics expressed by the requirements of pedagogical activity.

The following personal qualities are necessary for the future teacher to carry out his professional activity: creativity, technical thinking, confidence in his own strength, constantly improving his professional skills, being able to manage processes with emotional-firmness, the results of the emergence of professional competence are among them. **M.M. Kashapov** divided the stages of mental and professional development in the human youth into the following stages:

I. Pre-professional development.

- ❖ Pre-game development (up to 3 years);
- ❖ Game stage (pre-school childhood up to 3-7 years old);
- ❖ The stage of mastering educational activities (from 7-8 to 11-12 years old).

II. Development during career choice.

Optation stage (conscious preparation for life, work, career path planning, career choice period from 13-13 to 14-18 years old).

III. Development during professional training and attainment of future professional skills.

- ❖ Vocational education stage (15-19 or 16-23 years old);
- ❖ Professional adjustment stage (from 17-21 to 24-27 years old);
- ❖ Stage of development of professional skills (from 21-27 to 45-50 years old);
- ❖ The period of demonstration of professional skills (from 46-50 to 60-65 years);
- ❖ Decline stage (61-65 years).

Discussion.

In acmeology, a person is considered in his state of activity. Acting, personality as a system "fits" to other systems - life, activity, communication, cognition in general. Therefore, a person's activity should be carried out in accordance with the quality and criteria of each of the established systems. The activity presented by the society to its performer, the quality of the subject appears as a new, changed quality of the person, which means not only the matching of abilities, goals and his needs, but also a complete reconstruction of the entire system of his mental organization.

The subject of activity finds the ratio of external and internal determinations, necessity and freedom, regulation, standardization, standardization and individualization. The task of the subject is to resolve this contradiction in the current activity and in the entire active professional life of a person. Based on the principle of the subject of activity, acmeology, on the one hand, reveals the most complete and satisfactory ways of self-expression in various spheres of life, which is a prerequisite for creativity. On the other hand, this principle allows to ensure the highest social and professional efficiency of representatives of various specialties.

The principle of the subject of life and activity is historically, theoretically and logically clear and fundamental to acmeology. The acmeological approach for a modern educational institution is future-oriented and promising today, and its essence is that a comprehensive examination and restoration of the subject's integrity in order to influence the achievement of high goals, to achieve maturity. In the tooth, its characteristics of activity as an individual, a person and a subject are studied together with all the interrelationships and causes that give rise to it. This is one of the innovative approaches in education, and in order for the student to determine his personal acme, he develops strong motivations for his chosen specialty, and the motivation to achieve success or the need to achieve success in life. In preparing the student for professional activity, his personal qualities and qualities are manifested in his individual image.

Summary:

Application of advanced innovative approaches to education is one of the most urgent problems in the system. This requires improvement of the innovative environment of the industry and its forms, improvement of the activity of innovation centers. For this, it is necessary to analyze the technological processes and objective laws in the system from the point of view of development. Innovations in the educational system are the result of the integration of knowledge and acquired experience, which is reflected in the processes of science, education and production. This implies the implementation of innovation in the field, which is the basis of efficiency in the system. Innovative processes depend on several factors, such as the organization and management of a specific type of activity, the general level and

interests of specialists in the field, even the mentality of the nation, the state's policy in this field, scientific and educational achievements, and the potential of the educational system.

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